

Synthesis of some New 5-(2-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(1-acetyl-5-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)pyrazoles and 1-Phenyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(1-phenyl-5-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)pyrazoles

(MRS) B. D. SARAF* and K. N. WADODKAR

Department of Chemistry, Vidarbha Mahavidyalaya, Amravati-444 604

Manuscript received 4 October 1991, revised 19 January 1993, accepted 1 February 1993

In continuation of our work on novel and hitherto unknown heterocyclic system we wish to report herein the synthesis of 3,4,5-trisubstituted-pyrazoles in which the substituent at 4-position is either 1-acetyl or 1-phenyl-5-aryl-2-pyrazoline nucleus.

3,4,5-Trisubstituted-pyrazoles have been con-

veniently synthesised from 3-aryl-2-methylchromones by earlier workers^{1,5}. Baker and Butt¹ reported the formation of two isomers, viz. 4-acyl-3-methyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1-phenylpyrazole and 4-aryl-3,5-dimethyl-1-phenylpyrazole by the action of phenylhydrazine on 3-acyl-2-methylchromone. But

- a R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H
- b R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H, R₃ = OCH₃
- c R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = H
- d, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = OCH₃
- e, R₁ = R₃ = H, R₂ = CH₃
- f, R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₃, R₃ = OCH₃

Scheme 1 Reagents (i) Ac₂O/NaOAc (ii) NH₂NH₂ H₂O/AcOH, (iii) PhNHNH₂ HCl/C₂H₅N

another group² supported the formation of only the 4-acyl derivative. Whereas, others³⁻⁵ reported the formation of only the 4-arylpiperazines by the action of hydrazine and phenylhydrazine separately on 3-aryl-2-methylchromones.

In the present study novel results have been obtained by replacing the aryl group in 3-aryl-2-methylchromones by a cinnamoyl or *para*-substituted-cinnamoyl group, which certainly enhances its reactivity towards carbonyl reagents such as hydrazine and phenylhydrazine. Thus, 3-cinnamoyl-2-methylchromone was treated with hydrazine and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride separately. Instead of the expected pyrazoles, the products were identified as 5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(1-acetyl-5-aryl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)pyrazoles (**3a-f**) and 1-phenyl-5-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-3-methyl-4-(1,5-diphenyl-2-pyrazolin-3-yl)pyrazoles (**4a-f**) respectively (Scheme 1). Hence, it appears that the cinnamoyl moiety at 4-position in the initially formed pyrazole nucleus further reacts with the reagent to form the products.

These results support the enhanced reactivity of the cinnamoyl group as against an aryl group in 3-aryl-2-methylchromones.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Digilab FTS 14 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 202 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (80 MHz, CDCl₃) on a Varian CFT-20 instrument using TMS as the internal standard. C, H and N analyses were found satisfactory for all compounds. The required 1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl-4-penten-1,3-diones (**1a-f**) were prepared by literature method⁶.

Preparation of 2a-f: A mixture of **1a** (2 g), acetic anhydride (20 ml) and fused sodium acetate (0.5 g) was heated in an oil-bath at 160° for 20 min, then cooled and diluted with water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as white wooly crystals (2 g), m.p. 168° (Found; C, 78.7; H, 5.1, C₂₀H₁₆O, requires: C, 78.9; H, 5.2 %); $\nu_{\max}$ 1 650, 1 640, 1 620 (C=O), 1 570 (C=C), 1 390 and 1 360 cm⁻¹ (pyrone oxide or γ -pyrone); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 230 and 310 nm; δ 2.42 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.49 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.18 (1H, d, CH=CH), 7.51 (1H, d, CH=CH) and 7.2-7.65 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other chromones were prepared: **2b** (78%), m.p. 145°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 650, 1 630, 1 600, 1 570, 1 390 and 1 360 cm⁻¹; δ 2.42 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.46

(3H, s, CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, ArOCH₃) and 6.85-7.48 (9H, m, ArH and CH=CH); **2c** (75%), 166°, **2d** (78%), 155°; **2e** (80%), 140°; **2f** (76%), 164°.

Preparation of 3a-f: A mixture of **2a** (0.005 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in acetic acid (25 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained on cooling and diluting the reaction mixture, was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as white powder (67%), m.p. 225° (Found: C, 70.2; H, 6.0; N, 14.9. C₂₂H₂₂O₂N₄ requires: C, 70.5; H, 5.8; N, 14.9 %); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 140 (OH), 3 060 (NH), 1 620 (N-COCH₃) and 1 520 (C-N) cm⁻¹; $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 230 and 280 nm; δ 2.1 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.63 (1H, dd, 20 and 4 Hz, H_A), 3.35 (1H, dd, 20 and 12 Hz, H_B), 5.27 (1H, dd, 12 and 4 Hz, H_X), 6.64-7.4 (8H, m, ArH) and 9.1 (1H, br, NH).

Similarly, other pyrazoles were prepared: **3b** (69%), m.p. 240°; **3c** (65%), 200°; **3d** (67%), 240°; **3e** (65%), 255°; **3f** (68%), 250°.

Preparation of 4a-f: A mixture of **2a** (0.005 mol) and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (0.015 mol) in pyridine (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water and acidified with 1:1 aqueous HCl. The resulting gummy mass was washed with water, triturated and crystallised from (1:1) ethanol-acetic acid mixture to get the product (58%), m.p. 161° (Found: C, 79.7; H, 5.7; N, 11.2. C₃₂H₂₈ON₄ requires: C, 79.33; H, 5.78; N, 11.57%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 320 (OH), 3 060-3 020 (C-H) and 1 590-1 600 (C=N); $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 210 and 270 nm; δ 2.1 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.69 (1H, dd, 18 and 8 Hz, H_A), 3.48 (1H, dd, 18 and 12 Hz, H_B), 5.02 (1H, dd, 12 and 8 Hz, H_X) and 6.5-7.3 (18H, m, ArH).

Similarly, other pyrazoles were prepared: **4b** (60%), 230°; **4c** (55%), 155°; **4d** (60%) 190°; **4e** (56%), 160°; **4f** (60%), 120°; δ 2.15 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.58 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.52 (1H, dd, 18 and 8 Hz, H_A), 3.27 (1H, dd, 18 and 12 Hz, H_B), 4.85 (1H, dd, 12 and 8 Hz, H_X) and 6.6-7.2 (17H, m, ArH).

References

1. W. BAKIR and V. S. BUTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2142
2. K. A. THAKAR and V. N. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 1059
3. M. G. JOSHI, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1983
4. S. B. NAIR, Ph.D. Thesis, Nagpur University, 1986
5. M. V. PARANJPE, Ph.D. Thesis, Amravati University, 1986
6. H. J. GAGGAD, K. N. WADODKAR and B. I. GHYIA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 1244
7. B. V. IOFFI, *Khim. Geterotsykl. Soedin.*, 1968, 6, 1089 (*Chem. Abstr.* 1969, 70, 72338).